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Perceived burdensomeness, thwarted belongingness and suicidal ideation in patients with fibromyalgia and healthy subjects: a cross-sectional study

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Abstract

Perceived burdensomeness and thwarted belongingness are key factors in the development of suicidal behaviors that have been frequently observed among patients with fibromyalgia. The aim of the present study was to compare these two factors in patients with fibromyalgia with and without suicidal ideation and healthy subjects. Secondary objectives were to evaluate the relationship between these two factors and the secondary variables included in the study, such as depression, sleep quality or the degree of marital adjustment. Perceived burdensomeness and thwarted belongingness were assessed with the Interpersonal Needs Questionnaire, depression and suicidal ideation with the Patients Health Questionnaire-9, suicidal risk with the Plutchik Suicide Risk scale, sleep with the Insomnia Severity Index, and marital adjustment with the Locke–Wallace Marital Adjustment scale. Questionnaire scores were compared with the Kruskal–Wallis test. 49 healthy subjects, 38 patients with fibromyalgia without suicidal ideation and 15 patients with fibromyalgia and suicidal ideations were included. Perceived burdensomeness scores were significantly higher in patients with suicidal ideation than in patients without suicidal ideation and controls; thwarted belongingness scores were significantly higher in patients with suicidal ideation than in controls. Marital adjustment was also significantly poor in patients with suicidal ideation than in patients without suicidal ideation and controls. Among patients with fibromyalgia, perceived burdensomeness seems to be strongly related with suicidal ideation, whereas thwarted belongingness seems to play a less relevant role at this respect. Poor marital adjustment could be related with depression.

Keywords

Fibromyalgia · Suicidal ideation · Perceived burdensomeness · Thwarted belongingness · Marital adjustment

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Introduction

Suicide is a social problem and a leading cause of death that, in many situations, could be prevented [1]. Data from 84,850 adult subjects from 17 countries included in the World Mental Health (WHO) Survey [2] suggest that the worldwide lifetime mean prevalence of suicidal ideation (hereafter SI) ranged from 3.0 to 15.9% (mean and SD: 9.2 ± 29.1), while the prevalence of suicide attempts ranged from 1.0 to 5.0% (mean and SD: 2.7 ± 29.1). The most prevalent worldwide risk factors associated with non-fatal suicidal behaviors are female sex, younger age, low educational level and mental disorder [2]. Likewise, separations and divorces increased three times SI and eight times suicidal attempts, while having a partner was shown to be a protective factor [3]. Another relevant risk factor for suicidal behaviors is insomnia [4].

Pain, and more specifically chronic pain, has also received attention in the scientific literature as a risk factor for suicidal behaviors [5]. Although most chronic pain diseases are not lethal, they can seriously affect the function and quality of life. In 1999, Fishbain found an association between chronic pain and suicide [6]. Later on, Fishbain et al. confirmed that SI and suicide plans were frequent among chronic pain patients [7] and the suicide rate for this population was found to be significantly greater than the one of the general population [8]. Several authors reviewed the studies that evaluated the risk factors associated with suicidal behaviors in chronic pain patients, and consistently found an association between some pain-related variables, such as intensity and duration of pain, origin and type of pain, pain catastrophizing and pain status, and insomnia [8–10].

Fibromyalgia (hereafter FM) is a chronic syndrome characterized by generalized pain, fatigue, sleep disturbances, morning stiffness, depressive symptoms and hypersensitivity to physical and physiological stimuli [11]. The global prevalence of FM is 2.7%, and it is more frequent among women [12]. Several studies have indicated a higher prevalence of suicidal behaviors in patients with FM, including SI [13–15], suicide attempts [16], and death by suicide [17, 18]. Although those suffering from FM may experience life weariness, this should not necessarily be understood as a desire to die [10]. Therefore, the desire to die must be mediated or moderated by other variables inherent or related to condition of pain.

Since 2005, the ideation to action framework [19] has proliferated as a scientific approach of the suicidal phenomenon from two differentiable but related processes; on the one hand, the factors responsible for SI and, on the other hand, the decisive factors in the progression from SI to suicidal action [19]. This perspective provides a structure for the future explanatory models and intervention programs [20]. The Interpersonal Theory of Suicide, developed by Joiner [21] was the first to emphasize the distinction between the two processes. Later on, Van Orden et al. [22] used this theory to emphasize the existence of two interpersonal constructs related to the development of SI: perceived burdensomeness (hereafter PB), for others or for oneself, and thwarted belongingness (hereafter TB), referring to the unmet need of feeling socially

integrated. According to the authors, SI emerges from the simultaneous presence of these two states and the sense of despair or perception that they will not change.

The above-mentioned studies evaluated the association among PB and TB with SI. This relationship has not been previously evaluated in patients with FM. For this reason, the main objective of the present study was to evaluate the differences in the scores of the two interpersonal factors related to the development of SI, i.e. PB and TB, in FM patients, with and without SI, and in healthy controls. Secondary objectives included to evaluate, in the same groups, the relationship between both factors of SI, and the secondary variables included in the study, such as depression, sleep quality, or the degree of marital adjustment.

Methods

The study, of a cross-sectional design, was performed including a group of patients with FM and healthy subjects as a control group (hereafter CRL). All patients signed the informed consent to participate in the study and the study protocol was approved by the Human Research Ethics Committee of the University of Granada.

Subjects

Inclusion criteria for all participants were to be aged ≥ 18 years and to be able to understand and complete the questionnaires. Patients were required to be diagnosed with FM according to the American College of Rheumatology 1990 Criteria [23]. Exclusion criteria for the CRL subjects were to present a mental health disease diagnosed and/or treated by a psychiatrist, or chronic painful disease. Patients were recruited from several FM associations, and healthy subjects were recruited among friends and relatives of the patients to gather a sample of similar sociodemographic characteristics.

Outcome measures

Interpersonal Needs Questionnaire (INQ)

The main outcome variable was the Interpersonal Needs Questionnaire (INQ) [24], a Spanish-validated of a 12-item English-version was used for this study [25]. The first seven items assess PB with scores ranging from 7 to 49 points and the following five items assess TB with scores ranging from 7 to 35 points; higher score values indicate higher degrees of PB and TB.

Patients Health Questionnaire-9 (PHQ-9)

This tool is part of the Primary Care Evaluation of Mental Disorders (PRIME-MD) that diagnose the five most common mental disorders presented in the population. This 9-item questionnaire evaluates the depressive symptomatology. The total scores range from 0 to 27 with higher values indicating more severe depression and a cut-off point of 10 was established to detect a clinically relevant depression. A positive answer in the 9th or i item ("Thoughts that you would be better off dead or hurting yourself in some way?") was considered as an indicator of SI. The

severity of the depression was assessed with the response to the questions 1–8, which is commonly known as PHQ-8 questionnaire. The Spanish-validated version was used [26].

Plutchik Suicide Risk Scale

This scale measures the degree to which a person expresses similar or associated characteristics to a suicidal behavior. This 15-item questionnaire ranges 1–15 points, with higher values indicating higher suicidal risk; a cut-off point of 6 for substantial suicide risk was established in the Spanish-validated version [27].

Insomnia Severity Index (ISI)

This tool measures the severity of insomnia in a 7-item questionnaire. ISI assesses self-perception of people with insomnia symptoms as well as the distress caused by sleeping problems. The total score ranges from 0 up to 28 points with higher values indicating more relevant sleeping problems and being 10 the cut-off point for detecting insomnia cases [28]. The Spanish-validated version of this questionnaire was used [29].

Locke and Wallace Marital Adjustment Test (LWMAT)

This scale measures marital satisfaction status with 15 items and in 3 different parts. The range scores from 0 to 158 points, higher scores indicating better marital satisfaction and being the cut-off point 94 in Spanish-speaking population as indicative of a satisfactory marital relationship. A validated Spanish-version was applied [30].

Statistical analysis

Student t test, Fisher's test and Chi-square test were used to analyse sociodemographic variables. Kruskal–Wallis test was used for comparison among groups, applying the Dunn's test for multiple comparisons within groups. Binary logistic regression analysis was used to estimate the relative risks of SI and suicide risk in patients with FM after adjusting the sociodemographic variables, i.e. age, sex, marital status, employment situation, and educational level. Partial correlation coefficients between the main and the secondary variables were calculated after controlling the sociodemographic data. Statistical analyses were performed with SPSS v.22 (IBM Corporation, Armonk, NY, USA) and GraphPad Prism v.5.04. It was assumed statistical significance when $p < 0.05$.

Results

A total of 116 questionnaires were collected but 14 of them were discarded due to a defective filling. Thus, the sample included a total of 102 subjects, 53 from patients with FM (FM) and 49 from healthy subjects (CRL).

The main sociodemographic variables are shown in Table 1. Mean age (52 ± 8.2) in the FM group was significantly higher ($p < 0.05$) than the one in the CRL group (47.6 ± 11.7). Both

groups also differed in educational level with a significant difference ($p < 0.01$), being university studies more frequent in the CRL group (49%), and primary studies in the FM group (54.7%). Likewise, employment status showed a significant difference ($p < 0.01$) with more people working in the CRL group (73.5%) than in the FM group, in which temporal or permanent disability and retired people due to illness predominated.

Table 2 shows the scores of the different questionnaires in the CRL group and in patients with FM with and without SI. In relation to the factors of the INQ questionnaire, PB scores were significantly higher in patients with FM than in CRL; there were also significant differences between patients with FM with and without SI. However, TB scores were only significantly different in patients with FM and SI in relation to CRL subjects.

Statistically significant differences were found for every secondary outcome variable between patients with FM with or without SI and CRL subjects. No statistically significant differences were found between FM patients with and without SI. In relation to the depression scores, we applied the cut-off point of 10 that has been suggested as indicative of clinically relevant depression [31] to establish that 44 out of 53 (81.1%) patients with fibromyalgia and 3 out of 49 (6.1%) controls experienced depression.

Table 3 shows the partial Pearson correlation coefficients observed between both INQ factors, i.e. PB and TB and the secondary variables, excepting LWMAT, which was filled only by married subjects, both in FM and in CRL groups after adjusting the data for the sociodemographic data. Among patients, PB showed a significant correlation with SI, suicide risk and depression scores, but not with insomnia scores, whereas TB was significantly correlated only with suicide risk and depression scores. In the CRL group, PB was significantly correlated with suicide risk, depression and insomnia severity scores, and TB was significantly correlated only with suicide risk scores. There was a significant correlation between PB and TB both in FM patients ($r = 0.393$, $p < 0.001$) and in CRL subjects ($r = 0.392$, $p < 0.001$). SI was reported by 15 (28.3%) patients with FM and none of the healthy subjects ($p < 0.01$).

As no control healthy subject scored positively in the 9th or i item of the PHQ-9, to estimate the relative risk for suicidal ideation it was assumed the hypothetical situation that only one single subject had positively answered to this item. After the data adjustment for age, sex, marital status, employment situation and educational level, odd ratios were significantly higher in FM patients than in healthy CLR, both for SI ($p = 0.005$) and for suicidal risk ($p < 0.001$) (Table 4).

Discussion

The main objective of our study was to evaluate the differences in the scores of the two interpersonal factors related to the development of SI, i.e. PB and TB, in patients with FM and in healthy controls. To this aim, we used the Interpersonal Needs Questionnaire (INQ), designed as a useful tool for measuring these social constructs, which were considered as predictors of the desire to commit suicide [24].

Several studies have evaluated the relevance of PB and/or TB in relation to SI in patients with chronic pain, although none of them detailed the types of chronic pain experienced by the patients [32–35]. All of them found that PB was a significant predictor of SI in patients with chronic pain, although data regarding TB were conflicting. Our data show highly significant

differences in PB between FM and CRL groups ($p < 0.001$), as well as between FM patients with SI, which was determined by a positive answer in the 9th or 10th item of the PHQ-9 (“Thoughts that you would be better off dead or hurting yourself in some way?”) compared to FM patients without SI ($p < 0.001$). PB showed a strong and significant correlation with SI, depression scores, and suicide risk in FM group. These data support the hypothesis that PB plays a key role in the development of suicidal behaviors and agree with the results of previous studies performed in samples of different clinical samples of patients [36], older people [37–39], military personnel [40, 41], Mexican women [42] and American Indians [43]. However, TB scores were only significantly higher in FM patients with SI compared to healthy CRL subjects ($p < 0.01$) and showed a strong and statistically significant correlation with depression scores and suicide risk, but not with SI. These data support previous findings suggesting that TB seems to be secondary importance in relation to the development of suicidal behaviors [35]. In addition, a recent systematic review that analysed the studies evaluating PB, TB and capability for suicide found that PB was the most tested and supported factor, contributing a large amount of variance in suicide ideation, whereas TB contributed a smaller amount of variance in suicide ideation [44].

In agreement with previous studies, our data support that suicidal behaviors are frequent among patients with FM, who have higher frequency of presentation of SI and suicide risk in comparison with healthy subjects. Calandre et al. [16] applied a survey to 180 FM patients and found that 16.7% of them reported one or more previous suicide attempts, a percentage very higher than the expected worldwide lifetime prevalence of 2.7% [1, 2]. In addition, two large population-based studies, one performed in Denmark and the other one in the US, found that mortality by suicide was increased among FM patients compared not only to the general population [17, 18]. Several studies reported an increase in suicidal behaviors related either to chronic pain [5], as well as depression [2] and sleep disorders [4]. FM patients often suffer, in addition to chronic pain, symptoms related to depressive mood and/or poor sleep quality [11]; therefore, they share one or more risk factors for the development of suicidal behaviors.

Regarding couple relationship issues, those FM patients who showed SI reported significantly worse marital adjustment than healthy subjects and FM patients who did not showed SI. In fact, the mean value for the LWMAT in FM patients with SI was lower (80.9) than the value of 94, suggested as a cut-off point for Spanish-speaking population. A possible explanation to this finding could be the greater severity of depressive symptoms ($p < 0.01$), collected using the PHQ-8, in FM patients with SI (18.9 ± 4.3) compared to FM patients without SI (16.3 ± 5.8) and with healthy controls (5.3 ± 4.6). Several previous studies have emphasized the relationship between dissatisfaction and depression [45–48] and it was found that poor marital adjustment during the first year after wedding predicts the presence of depressive symptoms 1, 5, and even 5 years later [49].

Although several previous studies have approached the study of suicidal behaviors in different samples of patients with rheumatic diseases [50], including FM patients, to our knowledge this is the first study that has evaluated PB and TB in FM patients, and their relation to SI, and the first one that has assessed marital adjustment in these patients. Despite these strengths, our study has also some limitations that must be acknowledged.

One of these limitations is the limited sample size. Although we were able to find significant differences between FM patients and healthy CRL for most of the parameters analysed in the study, a larger sample may provide greater strength to these findings. In addition, only 38 healthy subjects and 40 FM patients had a stable partner at the time of the study, which did

not allow us to obtain remarkable differences in the variable of marital adjustment. Another relevant limitation was not to consider the comorbidities of the FM patients, nor the degree to which they could be interfering with SI. Future studies should take into account the clinical heterogeneity of these patients to determine how the intensity or duration of symptoms, such as depression, or the presence of other associated pathologies, can interfere with the PB and, therefore, increase the suicidal behaviors and the risk of suicide in FM patients. It also must be remembered that there were statistically significant differences between FM patients and CRL subjects in relation to age; however, we do not think that these differences were clinically relevant for the purpose of the study, as most of the subjects in each group were of middle age.

Conclusions

The results of our study show that SI ideation is frequent among patients with fibromyalgia and that SI is strongly related with burdensomeness, a fact that was previously suggested in studies of patients with pain-related health complaints [32–35] but not in patients with fibromyalgia. Although SI do not always lead to a suicide attempt, either failed or successful, its presence constitutes a sign of alert for the prevention of more harmful suicidal behaviors. As the feeling of being a burden for relatives and friends is a factor easy to assess for the physician, it could help him to notice patients at risk of SI. These patients should be referred to mental health services to be adequately evaluated and, if necessary treated. Such prevention measures could be useful to decrease the excess of mortality by suicide associated with fibromyalgia [17, 18]. The evaluation of FM patients should consider the neurocognitive, psychological, physical and functional dimensions [51]. Within this overall assessment, evaluating the empirically supported aspects of the ideation to action framework could have an impact on better prevention and intervention. An example of this approach is that was proposed by Anestis et al. [52], which shows how the application of these theories might provide more efficient interventions than current efforts to reduce suicidal behavior.

On the other hand, the finding that SI is also associated with a poor marital relationship, despite the limited sample size, is interesting. As stated before, having a partner has been shown to be a protective factor for suicidality [1], whereas a defective marital relationship has been related with depression [45–49], the factor than has been shown to be more closely related to suicidal behaviors in patients with fibromyalgia [23, 25, 40, 51]. Future studies with larger samples sizes exploring the relationship between the degree of marital adjustment and the risk of suicide should be worthy to be undertaken.

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Author contributions: CPLC: recruitment and assessment of patients, creation of the first manuscript draft. JLOC, JMGL and MSM: data analysis and results; revision of the manuscript final draft. EPC: study concept and design, revision of the manuscript final draft.

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Table 1

Sociodemographic variables of the participants

	CRL (<i>n</i> = 49) [<i>n</i> (%)]	FM (<i>n</i> = 53) [<i>n</i> (%)]	<i>p</i> value
Age (mean ± SD)	47.6 ± 11.7	52.0 ± 8.2	0.0287*
Sex			0.2563**
Female	44 (90)	51 (96)	
Male	5 (10)	2 (4)	
Marital Status			0.4596**
Married/de facto	32 (65.3)	37 (69.8)	
Single/divorced/widowed	16 (32.7)	15 (28.3)	
Parental situation			0.8070**
Children	38 (77.7)	43 (81.1)	
No children	11 (22.4)	10 (18.9)	
Educational status			< 0.001***
No school/primary school	9 (18.4)	29 (54.7)	
Secondary school	17 (34.7)	15 (28.3)	
University	24 (49)	9 (16.9)	
Employment status			< 0.0001***
Work at home	4 (8.2)	6 (11.3)	
Work outside home	36 (73.5)	16 (30.2)	
Unemployed	6 (12.2)	7 (13.2)	
Temporary sick leave	0 (0)	6 (11.3)	
Permanent sick live	0 (0)	1 (20.8)	
Retired	3 (6.1)	7 (13.2)	

Bold numbers highlight relevant differences among groups

CRL healthy subjects, *FM* patients with fibromyalgia*Student *t* test, **Fisher's test, ***Chi-square test

Table 2

Differences in scores between control subjects, patients without suicidal ideation and patients with suicidal ideation (range and median values)

Questionnaires (range)	CRL (<i>n</i> = 49)	FM without suicidal ideation (<i>n</i> = 38)	FM with suicidal ideation (<i>n</i> = 15)	<i>p</i> value (global comparison)
INQ—Burdensomeness (1–49)	14 (6–35)	16.5 (9–43)***	32 (14–38)***#	<0.0001
INQ—Thwarted belongingness (1–35)	11 (5–31)	15.5 (5–32)	19 (7–29)**	0.0066
PHQ-8 (0–27)	3 (0–13)	13 (4–22)****	20 (10–27)****	<0.0001
Plutchik (0–15)	2 (0–8)	7 (2–13)***	10 (4–11)***	<0.0001
ISI (0–28)	4 (0–14)	17 (0–26)***	17 (13–28)***	<0.0001
LWMAT (0–158)	122.5 (74–146) <i>n</i> = 38	115 (38–147) <i>n</i> = 27	79* (6–153) <i>n</i> = 13	=0.0271

CRL controls; FM fibromyalgia patients; INQ Interpersonal Needs Questionnaire; PHQ-8 patients health questionnaire; Plutchik Plutchik Suicide Risk Scale; ISI Insomnia Severity index; LWMAT Locke–Wallace marital adjustment test (filled only by participants married or living with a stable partner)

Differences between patients with fibromyalgia and controls *****p* < 0.0001; ****p* < 0.0005; ***p* = 0.0065; **p* = 0.0424

Differences between patients with fibromyalgia with and without suicidal ideation #*p* = 0.0076

Table 3

Partial correlation coefficients between the mail and secondary variables after controlling the effect of sociodemographic variables (i.e. age, sex, marital status, employment situation, and educational level)

	INQ Thwarted belongingness	Plutchik	PHQ-8	ISI	PHQ <i>i</i> item
FM					
INQ Burdensomeness					
<i>r</i>	0.393	0.539	0.541	0.085	0.499
<i>p</i>	0.005	< 0.001	< 0.001	0.557	< 0.001
INQ Thwarted belongingness					
<i>r</i>	–	0.634	0.481	0.051	0.211
<i>p</i>	–	< 0.001	< 0.001	0.726	0.142
CRL					
INQ Burdensomeness					
<i>r</i>	0.392	0.420	0.443	0.355	–
<i>p</i>	0.007	0.004	0.002	0.016	–
INQ Thwarted belongingness					
<i>r</i>	–	0.337	0.176	0.057	–
<i>p</i>	–	0.022	0.242	0.706	–

Bold numbers highlight statistically significant partial correlation coefficients ($p < 0.05$)

CRL healthy controls; *FM* fibromyalgia patients; *INQ* Interpersonal Needs Questionnaire; *Plutchik* Plutchik Suicide Risk Scale; *PHQ-8* Patients Health Questionnaire; *ISI* Insomnia Severity Index, *PHQ i item* indicator of suicidal ideation

Table 4

Relative risk index of suicidal ideation and suicidal risk in fibromyalgia patients

	OR in FM	95% CI	<i>p</i> value
Suicidal ideation ^a	19.054	2.405–150.935	0.005
Suicide risk	30.055	10.247–100.269	<0.001

OR odds ratio; *FM* fibromyalgia patients; *CI* confidence intervals

^aAs no control subject scored positively in the 9th item of the PHQ-9, to estimate the relative risk for suicidal ideation, it was assumed that one single subject had positively answered to this item